

POPULATION AWARENESS: IN RELATION TO SEX, LEVEL OF EDUCATION AND LOCALITY

Dr. Kiran Luthra

Principal,

Dogra College of Education

Bari Brahmana, Jammu 180004 (J&K STATE)

Abstract

The population explosion has been found eroding the economic, social, cultural and ecological benefits and creating a situation which led to unemployment, pollution, poverty, ignorance and disequilibrium in the social set up. This has given rise to the issues of demographic, social, economic and educational change to ensure quality of life. The aim of present study was to see the effect of sex, levels of education and locality on population awareness. Interaction between sex, levels of education and locality on population awareness has been observed. The present study was based upon a sample of 1200 teachers working at primary and secondary levels of education. Simple random sampling technique was used. Standardized tools were employed for the collection of data. Parametric techniques were used for the analysis of data. Results were inpreted in light of given research questions..Conclusions have been drawn on the basis of results obtained in the present study.

Keywords:

Population Explosion, demographic, Social Security, Quality of Life

Introduction

The concept of population education has emerged due to limitless population growth and interaction with the social, economic and political aspects of human life .It has retarded the growth of our nation and created an imbalance between national income and expenditure .It has created many social problems. Undoubtedly, the population explosion

has become a challenge for us. The gravity of problem is such that if it is not tackled on a war footing, there is a little chance of permanent peace and security in the world .This problem of unlimited numbers is a concern to the world as a whole and to individual country like India.

All these problems call for a positive population policy and population education in order to regulate the rate of population. Keeping in view, the resources endowment and technological feasibility, sustained efforts have to be made over a considerable period of time to achieve positive results. Sattarshakwala,(1981) reported and it is interesting to note that firstly he prepared and tried out an Attitude Scale to know the attitude of the students, people in general and field workers in the family planning programme towards population education and then study the effect of a multimedia learning package on their attitude towards population education . The learning package prepared by Urmila Manavati was used for instruction .It was observed that the whole group that was exposed to the treatment of the learning package showed significant positive improvement (.01 levels) in their attitude towards population education. Mehta (1974) in an investigation had found that education helped in the formation of positive attitude towards population issues. Maheshwari J.R (1972) conducted a study and observed that majority of the teachers favoured the idea of integrating population education concepts with existing school subjects. They feel that most of the concepts could be integrated through social studies, science, languages and mathematics. Romili (1977) It is interesting to know that Romili also conducted study and stated that a reduction in the birth rate among poor people could not reasonably be expected unless countries provided their citizens with adequate minimum levels of education, health services and economic and social security.

Need and objectives

The students should be made to understand that certain economic, scientific or technological changes which are so necessary for raising the standard of living of all our people, would not succeed on their own unless and until every individual also is ready to change his views, values and life styles .First of all, the students should be made to

Understand the magnitude of the problem and its innumerable social, psychological and economic consequences. This needs instituting a course in demography, social and economic development and social values, health hygiene and nutrition, family life education, quality of life and environmental issues. The purpose of the present study is to increase knowledge, understanding and awareness and hopefully it shall help us to achieve wisdom in the conduct of our lives both individually and collectively. Bhandarkar K.M (1983) constructed a Population Education Knowledge Test and an Attitude Scale. It was observed in this study that by increasing students' knowledge of population education, a favourable attitude can be developed among them towards population education

Keeping in view the present scenario it tempted the investigator to construct and standardize the Population Awareness Test. On the basis of this test, one can visualize the people from different segments of the society on the variables of sex, levels of education, locality, in relation to their concept and attitude regarding the population education and its awareness.

Aims of the study

1. To study the effect of sex, education and locality on demography
2. To study the effect of sex, education and locality on socio-economic development
3. To study the effect of sex, education and locality on family life education
4. To study the effect of sex, education and locality on health, hygiene and nutrition
5. To study the effect of sex, education and locality on quality of life
6. To study the effect of sex, education and locality on environmental issues

Hypothesis

1. There is significant difference between sex, education and locality on demography
2. There is significant difference between sex, education and locality on socio-economic development

3. There is significant difference between sex, education and locality on family life education
4. There is significant difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on health, hygiene and nutrition
5. There is significant difference between sex, education and locality on quality of life
6. There is significant difference between sex, education and locality on environmental issues

Delimitations

The effect of three independent variables namely sex, levels of education and locality on dependent variables (PAS) was only studied. Other variables were not included in the present study.

Sampling

The random sampling technique was used. The total sample taken for present investigation was comprised of 1200 teachers working at primary and secondary levels of education of Jammu Province.

Tools used

Population Awareness Test (PAT) prepared by investigator herself was used. It was a five point scale based on Likert type. Items selected and included in the test were from the broad spectrum of population education which include demographic, social and economic development and social values, health hygiene and nutrition, family life education, quality of life and environmental issues.

Statistical Techniques Employed

ANOVA was employed to see the effect of Independent variables (sex, levels of education and locality) on the dependent variable (population awareness test score).

Researcher applied Analysis of variance introduced by Fisher R.A. A factorial design 2 x 2 x 2 was prepared to see the effect of three independent variables on a dependent variable. The F- ratios against different sources of variance for 2 x 2 x 2 factorial design were calculated.

Analysis of Data

The independent variables were (1) sex (2) levels of education and (3) Locality and the dependent variables were scores of the six areas namely – (1) Demography, (2) Social and Economic Development and Social Values, (3) Health, Hygiene and Nutrition, (4) Family Life Education, (5) Quality of Life, and (6) environmental issues of population awareness.. The analysis of variance was designed to calculate the main effects A, B, C corresponding to sex, locality and levels of education respectively, the double interaction effects A X B, A X C, B X C and the triple interaction effects A X B X C. The values of within treatments were also calculated. The computed values of all these effects and the 'F' ratios are given in Table A, B, C, D, E, F area wise as follows.

Table – 1

Significance of Difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on Demography (Summary of 2³ Analysis of Variance)

education is power

Source of Variation	Sum of square S.S.	Df	Mean Variance M.S.	F-Ratio	Required F-Ratio
A Sex	56.1	1	56.1	1.27	3.97 – 7.00
B Locality	973.0	1	973.0	21.94*	3.97 – 7.00
C Levels of Edu.	12.0	1	12.0	0.27	3.97 – 7.00
A x B Sex and locality	221.1	1	221.1	4.99**	3.97 – 7.00

A X C	99.0	1	99.0	2.23	3.97 – 7.00
Sex & levels of Edu.					
B X C	221.1	1	221.1	4.99**	3.97 – 7.00
Locality x Levels of Edu.					
A x B X C	9.1	1	9.1	0.21	3.97 – 7.00
Sex, locality and levels of education					
Within treatment	3192.5	72	44.3		3.97 – 7.00

* Significant at .01 level

** Significant at .05 level

RESULTS: Table -1 shows that

- There was insignificant difference between male and female on demographic awareness scores
- There was insignificant difference on demographic awareness scores on the basis of levels of education
- Significant difference had been found between localities on demographic awareness scores at 0.01 level
- Interaction between locality and education, locality and sex had been found significant on demographic awareness scores at 0.05 level

Table – 2

Significance of Difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on Socio-Economic Development Values (2³ Analysis of Variance)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares S.S.	Df	Mean Variance M.S.	F Ratio	Required F Ratio
A Sex	288.8	1	288.8	6.55**	3.97 – 7.00
B Locality	530.5	1	530.5	12.04*	3.97 – 7.00
C Levels of Edu.	18.1	1	18.1	0.41	3.97 – 7.00
A X B sex and locality	0.1	1	0.1	0.00	3.97 – 7.00
A X C sex and levels of Education	48.1	1	48.1	1.09	3.97 – 7.00
B X C levels of Education and Locality	336.2	1	336.2	7.63*	3.97 – 7.00
A X B X C Sex, locality and levels of education	80.0	1	80.0	1.82	
Within	3550.2	72	49.3		
Total	4851.8	79			

* Significant at .01 level

** Significant at .05 level

RESULTS: Table -2 reveals that

- There was significant difference between male and female on socio-economic development at 0.05 level
- There was insignificant difference on socio-economic development and values scores on the basis of levels of education at 0.01 level
- Significant difference had been found between localities and socio-economic development and values scores
- Interaction between locality and education had been found significant at 0.01 level on socio-economic development and values

Table – 3

Significance of Difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on Health Hygiene and Nutrition (2³ Analysis of Variance)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares S.S.	Df	Mean Variance M.S.	F Ratio	Required F Ratio
A Sex	204.8	1	204.8	4.65**	3.97 – 7.00
B Locality	26.5	1	16.5	0.6	3.97 – 7.00
C Levels of Edu.	36.5	1	36.5	0.83	3.97 – 7.00
A X B sex and locality	8.5	1	8.5	0.19	3.97 – 7.00
A X C sex and levels of Education	211.3	1	211.3	4.79**	3.97 – 7.00

B X C	5.0	1	5.0	0.11	3.97 – 7.00
levels of Education and Locality					
A X B X C	72.2	1	72.2	1.64	3.97 – 7.00
Sex, locality and levels of education					
Within	2769.6	72	38.5		3.97 – 7.00
Total	3334.2	79			

* Significant at .01 level

** Significant at .05 level

RESULTS: Table -3 reflects that

- There was significant difference between male and female on health, hygiene and nutrition at 0.05 level
- There was insignificant difference between mean scores of the subjects on health, hygiene and nutrition in relation to localities, levels of education
- Significant difference had been found between localities and socio-economic development and values scores
- Interaction between sex and education had been found significant at 0.05 level on Health, hygiene and nutrition

Table – 4

Significance of Difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on Family Life Education (2³Analysis of Variance)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares S.S.	Df	Mean Variance M.S.	F-Ratio	Required F-Ratio
A Sex	9.1	1	9.1	0.21	3.97 – 7.00
B Locality	32.5	1	32.5	0.74	3.97 – 7.00
C Levels of Education	0.1	1	0.1	-	3.97 – 7.00
A X B sex and locality	0.1	1	0.1	-	3.97 – 7.00
A X C sex and levels of Education	17.1	1	17.1	0.39	3.97 – 7.00
B X C levels of Education and Locality	25.3	1	25.3	0.57	3.97 – 7.00
A X B X C Sex, locality and levels of education	148.5	1	148.5	3.37	3.97 – 7.00
Within	3720.7	72	51.7		
Total	3953.5	79			

Table-4 Shows that

- Insignificant difference had been found on the basis of sex, levels of education and locality on family life education

Table – 5

Significance of Difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on Quality of Life (2³Analysis of Variance)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares S.S.	Df	Mean Variance M.S.	F-Ratio	Required F-Ratio
Sex	4.0	1	4.0	0.09	3.97 – 7.00
Locality	12.0	1	12.0	0.29	3.97 – 7.00
Levels of Education	5.0	1	5.0	0.1	3.97 – 7.00
Interaction between sex and locality	96.8	1	96.8	2.20	3.97 – 7.00
Interaction between sex and levels of Edu.	28.8	1	28.8	0.65	3.97 – 7.00
Interaction between levels of education and locality	281.3	1	281.3	6.38**	3.97 – 7.00
Triple Interaction	48.1	1	48.1	1.09	3.97 – 7.00
Within	3226.8	72	45.1		-
Total	3702.8	79			

** Significant at .05 level

Table-5 reveals that:

- There was insignificant difference between sex, levels of education and locality on quality of life
- However, significant interaction had been found between levels of education and locality on quality of life at 0.05 level

Table – 6

Significance of Difference between Sex, Level of Education and Locality on Environmental Issues (2^3 Analysis of Variance)

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares S.S.	Df	Mean Variance M.S.	F-Ratio	Required F-Ratio
Sex	0.3	1	0.3	0.01	3.97 – 7.00
Locality	177.0	1	177.0	4.02**	3.97 – 7.00
Levels of Education	78.0	1	78.0	1.77	3.97 – 7.00
Interaction between sex and locality	82.0	1	82.0	1.86	3.97 – 7.00
Interaction between sex and levels of Edu.	5.5	1	5.5	0.13	3.97 – 7.00
Interaction between levels of education and locality	2.8	1	2.8	0.06	3.97 – 7.00

Triple Interaction	90.3	1	90.3	2.05	
Within	5128.9	72	71.2	-	
Total	5564.9	79			

** Significant at .05 level

Table-6 shows that

- There was insignificant difference between sex, levels of education on environmental issues
- However, significant difference had been found between localities on environmental issues

Result and Discussion

Findings and interpretation of the analysis of variance have been discussed as given below:-

The researcher can safely conclude from the results of statistical analysis that locality (Rural and Urban) was found significant in its role in affecting the scores of Demography, Social and Economic Development and Social values and Environmental issues. Findings of these studies were found dissimilar with the findings of SCERT Bihar (1986.) The Study conducted in Bihar revealed that message of population explosion had also reached to the rural areas in the same magnitude as it had been prevalent in urban locality .The reasons might be i.e. mass- media, adult education, newspaper, evening classes for raising the literacy percentage for better socio- economic status and for raising the standard of living of the people. Another factor namely sex (Male and Female) had been found significant in affecting the scores of Social and Economic development and Social Value and Health hygiene and Nutrition. Findings of these studies were found similar with the findings of Bhandarkar .1983). It was observed that all these differences

had gone in favour of female teachers which showed that although they were found busy in their domestic affairs still they had been very much concerned about population.

So far as interaction was concerned it had been observed that the cumulative effect of locality and levels of education were found affecting the scores on Demography, Social and Economic development and Social Values and Quality of life. It meant that the teachers belonging to Rural and Urban areas as well as working in primary and secondary levels of education differed significantly on Demography, Social and Economic development and Social Value and Quality of life. Further, it was observed that sex and locality as well as sex and levels of education were found affecting the scores of Demography and Health, Hygiene and Nutrition.

Suggestions

- Message of population explosion should be continuously communicated at a large scale
- The educational planners, policy makers, and professionals should be involved in designing various training programmes
- Teachers working at primary and secondary stages of education should be oriented on population awareness
- Longitudinal studies should be conducted to see the impact of education, area, and socio-economic development on population awareness

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